

WP3 – Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services

Deliverable 3.2: European Map and Inventory of Agroforestry Products and Services

Project name	DigitAF (101059794)
Work-package	3: Accounting agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries in agroforestry value chains
Deliverable	Deliverable 3.2: European map and inventory of agroforestry products and services (version 2)
Date of report	7 December 2024 (version 1) 30 October 2025 (version 2)
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Download	https://zenodo.org/records/15085471

DigitAF project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N°101059794. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Research Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 to June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims to support high-quality implementation of agroforestry in Europe to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. The project uses a participatory research approach to engage with actors involved in the development of agroforestry and to unlock synergies among stakeholders and other research to facilitate the implementation of innovations. The overall objective of the project is to provide three groups of stakeholders with digital tools that address their needs and expectations. The three groups are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national, and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the sequestered carbon and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

This Deliverable 3.2 (updated from version 1 from December 2024) forms part of work package 3 in the DigitAF project, which deals with verifying and accounting the benefits of agroforestry practices for stakeholders in the value chain. This report describes the progress towards the aim of developing a web-based European map of agroforestry, including suppliers and consultants. This aim was achieved bearing in mind the following three points:

1. Although there are existing mapping activities of agroforestry at a European level such as the maps on the AGFORWARD and European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF) websites, these have not been updated recently.
2. The national bodies represented in EURAF often organise and host national maps of agroforestry. These national maps support stakeholder involvement and visibility, and it was felt important to maintain this national interest.
3. However, there is currently no established means of collating those data to create a European map of agroforestry. Hence an approach was sought which brought together national stakeholders from several European countries to develop a common framework.

Therefore, we based our work on existing maps to identify their successes and their limits (Section 1.2). We then developed a methodology to collate data concerning different types of stakeholders, from different European countries (section 2). Finally, we collated data in Germany, UK and Ireland, the Netherlands, Italy and Belgium (section 2.2.4). The result of the process has been to create a comprehensive “Agroforestry Map of Europe” which is embedded on the DigitAF website (<https://digitaf.eu/agroforestry-map/>) (section 3.1), the development of new country maps (section 3.2). These results can be used to conduct country-wide and soon Europe-wide studies (section 3.3) and to foster networking among stakeholders (section 3.4). This report concludes with the presentation of the next steps regarding continuation of data collection and future maintenance of the map (section 3.5).

1.2 Existing maps

1. The AGFORWARD map of European agroforestry

An initial map of European agroforestry was developed as part of the EU FP7 project AGFORWARD (2014-2017) to promote agroforestry and highlight the distribution of demonstration agroforestry sites (Burgess and Rosati, 2018). The map's primary purpose was to demonstrate the location of agroforestry demonstration and experimental sites (Figure 1). In 2018, the map included 84 entries (AGFORWARD, 2024).

Figure 1. The AGFORWARD project developed a map of agroforestry experimental and demonstration sites across Europe (AGFORWARD, 2018).

The agroforestry systems were initially divided into four types of systems following a categorisation format used in the AGFORWARD project. These were agroforestry systems of high natural and cultural value, such as the Dehesa and Montado systems. A second category was high-value tree systems such as grazed orchards. The third category was the integration of trees into arable systems or silvoarable agroforestry, and the fourth category was the integration of trees into livestock systems or silvopastoral agroforestry (Palma et al., 2015). It can be noted that this categorization is incomplete, as it does not cover a whole range of agroforestry systems, such as food forest systems and forest gardens, riparian forests and other small woodland formations with specific functions.

2. The EURAF map of European agroforestry

Since the completion of the AGFORWARD project in 2017, the EURAF map of European agroforestry has been maintained by the board of EURAF with data provisions through the national delegates of the European federation (Figure 2) (EURAF, 2024).

Figure 2. EURAF map of European agroforestry (EURAF, 2024).

As of December 2024, the EURAF map included 230 agroforestry sites. Four of the five most common agroforestry types coincide with the four categories used in the AGFORWARD project. These include silvoarable systems ($n = 68$), silvopastoral systems ($n = 58$), high natural and cultural value systems ($n = 39$), and high-value tree systems ($n = 20$). In addition, there are a substantial number of food forest systems and forest gardens ($n = 33$). Systems on permanent grassland ($n = 8$) and mixed agrosilvopastoral systems ($n = 3$) were the least common agroforestry types on the map.

The high number of silvoarable sites contrasts with the analysis undertaken by den Herder et al. (2017) using the Land Use and Cover Area Frame Survey (LUCAS), which indicated that silvopastoral systems occupy the majority of the agroforestry area in Europe. The dominance of silvopastoral agroforestry is also emphasised in a recent analysis using the 2018 dataset (Rubio-Delgado et al., 2023). Therefore, the EURAF map is not representative of the actual diversity and distribution of European agroforestry systems. Furthermore, the EURAF map, based on a Google Maps, is not progressing due to a high level of maintenance and incurring difficulties in categorisation and standardisation and increased concerns over data protection.

2 Methodology for the creation of the new European map of agroforestry

2.1 The need for a new European map of agroforestry

As discussed, the existing EURAF map includes an increasing classification of agroforestry types and there is no formal method for new users to update entries on the map. These problems were identified during the submission of the DigitAF project. One of the overarching approaches practised during the DigitAF project is to promote the FAIR principles to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of digital resources (Tomás et al., 2024). Therefore, an objective in developing a new map was to bring together the developers of various existing national maps to agree a common baseline, thus allowing interoperability between maps and the collation of a European map of agroforestry. We also had to deal with European and national regulations regarding accessibility and data protection (European Union, 2016).

The German Agroforestry Association (DeFAF e.V.) explored possibilities for the development of a Europe-wide map, bringing together national mapping activities and using the German map as a prototype. Initially developed in the project IG AUFWERTEN a German agroforestry map was hosted and managed by DeFAF e.V. (2025).

Figure 3. Countries in the DigitAF and REFOREST projects developing the Agroforestry Map of Europe.

In preparation for the new Agroforestry Map of Europe, existing maps (AGFORWARD map, EURAF map, various national maps) were reviewed in order to collect the formats, classification of agroforestry types and metadata used. A preliminary list of categories from the review and technical parameters were presented and discussed during an online meeting on 24 January 2023. At that meeting, it was agreed that the new map should enable the searching for entries on the basis of criteria such as agroforestry system type, tree species, and spatial location.

The development of the new Agroforestry Map of Europe addressed three criteria. These were:

- To use a common framework, which will allow uniform visualisation and collation of European agroforestry information to create an online comprehensive map across Europe.
- To develop a technical protocol to accommodate major European languages to facilitate entry and use by agroforestry stakeholders in their national language format. Based on that, multilingual translations should be provided, and English should be used as the back-end language for easier maintenance.
- To collate the data so that it is fully compliant with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) rules within the European Union (European Union, 2016). This would also extend to the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) associated with uploaded photos.

In order to develop a common framework, staff from DigitAF worked with staff from the REFOREST project to allow increased spatial coverage of the map since the two projects combined cover most European countries (Figure 3). Hence, the new Agroforestry Map of Europe is a joint output of the two projects. The technical aspects of the programming activity are led by DeFAF.

2.2 Process for developing the map

1. Phase one: defining the scope and potential mapping categories

In 2023, DeFAF, working with partners in the DigitAF and REFOREST projects, agreed on a general process for establishing and updating the Agroforestry Map of Europe. To facilitate data management, it was decided that individual country delegates should primarily be responsible for the content and quality control of their national map, and that a way should be found whereby people who provided data at a national level could permit for the data to be displayed at a European level, e.g. on the EURAF website. Once the map is fully operational, individuals should be able to update the map directly at EURAF level or through national organisations represented within EURAF.

It was agreed that data should be added by individuals (e.g. farmers), organisations or businesses in the agroforestry value chain onto the national maps in their local language. The aim is, that each national organisation is in control of their data. In order to add a new entry an account containing a valid e-mail address will be created for the individual after clicking on the “Green Plus”-symbol in order to verify the entry and to allow an alteration or deletion of the entry at a later stage. Once an entry has been submitted, the national administrator receives an automated notification via e-mail about a new entry or a change request. The national administrator will then review the request and confirm or reject it. Then the system will send an acceptance link for confirmation, so that entries are double-checked by the person who first made the request. The final pin will appear on the map once clearance has been given (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Workflow of data entries for the new Agroforestry Map of Europe.

From the review of existing map ontologies, the updated categorisation of agroforestry systems was unified into four simple system types, compared to seven in the EURAF map (for example, the previously used categories “Silvopastoral Systems” and “Systems on Permanent Grassland” are often non-exclusive).

Figure 5. Complementarity of the three basic agroforestry systems (Hübner and Günzel, 2020).

The four system types are “silvoarable”, “silvopastoral”, “agrosilvopastoral” and “others” (e.g. food forests, kitchen gardens or urban agroforestry systems). In line with the objectives of WP3 in the DigitAF project, components of the value chain are also included. The map therefore locates stakeholders from businesses such as tree nurseries, equipment sales, planning or planting companies in the upstream sector, and product manufacturers in the downstream sector. Educational/ information organizations are also included in the new map. Interested parties (stakeholders currently thinking

about or planning an agroforestry system) can put themselves on the map with the possibility to “upgrade” these entries once the sites are established. This will remove the burden of creating entries twice and/or the need for manual deletion of sites with a status change.

DeFAF subcontracted the programming activity to DUKTIL, funded through the REFOREST project, who have programmed the map interface using NodeJS (JavaScript on the Server) for the back-end activities of the map, MongoDB for the database, and Angular (JavaScript framework) for the front-end (GUI).

2. Phase two: building the category system for cross European applicability

In early 2024, phase two focussed on the establishment of the most appropriate categories of data to be collected, giving project partners in DigitAF and REFOREST as well as external experts in the field the opportunity to contribute. The translation of all terms into 19 languages was undertaken with the initial aid of auto-translation, followed by manual verification of the correctness of translation by the representatives of EU countries; a crucial step considering most terms are very specific. From several languages, the auto-translation generated very general results from specific inputs. During this phase, participants were asked to make further adjustments and add categories that were iteratively added and colour-coded for better orientation.

Five online data entry forms were created for the verification of translations and completeness of terms, including:

1. Agroforestry sites (Table 1): The four categories of agroforestry systems are “silvoarable” (e.g. woody and arable crops), “silvopastoral” (e.g. woody crops and livestock incl. grazed permanent crops), “agrosilvopastoral” (e.g. woody, arable crops and livestock), and “others” (e.g. kitchen gardens and community food forests).
2. Landowners or farmers interested in establishing agroforestry (Table 2).
3. Public organisations involved in agroforestry (Table 3).
4. Organisations involved in agroforestry value chains (Table 4).
5. Potentially used tree and shrub species.

Although Form 5 for trees and shrubs is linked to the agroforestry system description (Form 1), Form 5 was kept separately due to a high volume of changes and additions sometimes linked to specific legal and funding issues. As of December 2024, the list of tree and shrubs in Form 5 form contains the botanic names of 136 tree and 56 shrub categories. These are mostly at the species level, however, important cultivars are included, as well as some tree and shrub species at the genus level.

Table 1. Data inputs for agroforestry sites.

Main category	Attributes
Meta data	title, ID, coordinates (Latitude, Longitude)
Short description	max. 2,000 characters
Address	street, house number, postcode, city, region, country
Contact	contact person, email, phone, website
Photos	upload
Agroforestry system type	silvoarable system / silvopastoral system / agrosilvopastoral system / other
Size of agroforestry system area(s) (in ha)	
Percentage of area under trees/shrubs (in %)	
Establishment (date)	
Tree species	
(Intended) use of trees	production of biofuel wood / production of timber / other material use / food production / environmental benefits / cultural benefits / other
Shrub species	
Intended use of shrubs	production of biofuel wood / production of timber / other material use / food production / medicinal and aromatic plants / environmental benefits / other
Livestock species in the agroforestry system	poultry / cattle /sheep (incl. goat) / pigs / other
Main crop types in the agroforestry system	field beans / field grass / vegetables / barley / oats / potatoes / grain peas / lupine / lucerne / corn, maize / oil flax / rapeseed / rye / sunflower / common wheat / sugar beet / durum wheat / mustard / intermediate wheatgrass / clover / spelt / grapevine / medicinal and aromatic plants / flowers and ornamental plants / other
Other agroforestry products	
Site specifics	drought, low water holding capacity / low soil fertility / susceptibility to erosion / species-poor site / landscape with few structures, landscape elements / other
Interest in product sales / marketing	yes / no
Motivation / reasons for establishing and maintaining agroforestry system	establish ecological balance, enhance biodiversity / higher productivity / soil health and erosion control / reduce substance input into surface waters / more diverse product range / contribution to climate protection, climate resilience / protective effect for livestock, improve animal welfare / landscape appearance, aesthetics
Farming sectors	arable farming / fodder production / livestock farming / energy production / fruit growing / wood production / direct sale available / agritourism offered / other

Table 2. Data inputs sought from respondents interested in agroforestry.

Main category	Attributes
Meta data	title, ID, coordinates (Latitude, Longitude)
Short description	max. 2,000 characters
Address	street, house number, postcode, city, region, country
Contact	contact person, email, phone, website
Photos	upload
Agroforestry system type	silvoarable system / silvopastoral system / agrosilvopastoral system / other
Motivation / rationale for establishing and maintaining agroforestry system	establish ecological balance, enhance biodiversity / higher productivity / improved marketing / soil health and erosion control / reduce substance input into surface waters / more diverse product range / contribution to climate protection, climate resilience / protective effect for livestock, improve animal welfare / landscape appearance, aesthetics / research, pilot site / other
Obstacles, barriers and other reasons for restraint	legal framework / lack of or insufficient support / ownership structure / lack of experience, information, counselling opportunities / lack of capital / uncertain economic returns / other

Table 3. Data inputs sought from public and governmental organisations active in agroforestry.

Main category	Attributes
Meta data	title, ID, coordinates (Latitude, Longitude)
Short description	max. 2,000 characters
Address	street, house number, postcode, city, region, country
Contact	contact person, email, phone, website
Photos	upload
Type of institution	university, college / research institution, institute / administration, public authority / association, federation, NGOs / demonstration farm / other
Main topics	economy / technology / law / ecology / area planting / planting material / other

Table 4. Data inputs sought from upstream and downstream organisations.

Main category	Attributes
Meta data	title, ID, coordinates (Latitude, Longitude)
Short description	max. 2000 characters
Address	street, house number, postcode, city, region, country
Contact	contact person, email, phone, website
Photos	upload
Type of institution	consultant or consulting firm / tree nurseries / contractors (providing planting or pruning services) / processors of agricultural products from agroforestry / wood processing facilities / sale of agroforestry products / sale of agricultural inputs and materials / education / trainings / and/or workshops / other
Main products	Mention the main products
Labelling and branding	Are you interested in branding or labelling? (Yes/No), We are using labelling already (Yes/No), We are interested in labelling (Yes/No)

3. Phase three: building country specific databases

The third phase of developing the map started in June 2024 with the distribution of the country-specific data collection forms for each country individually to a contact from the project and in some cases, affiliated representative organisation (Table 5). Access to each country's data sheet needed authentication, hence minimising the cross-spill of information across countries. Additional data entries in the national forms were thus made available for bulk-data import before the launch of the map.

To support the integration of existing data from the EURAF map, all publicly available information was transposed from a KML file into the new data format and redistributed across the national data forms. However, the information was of different quality and information needed a verification and addition of missing data. A comparison of data from the EURAF map with that from the national maps showed some distinct entries and some entries that overlapped. In the development of the new European map of agroforestry, the process means that the new entries have been checked by national representatives.

Table 5. List of organisations gathering data for the Agroforestry Map of Europe.

Country	Project partner organisation
BE	<i>Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw – En Visserijonderzoek (ILVO)</i> – Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
BE	<i>Association pour l'agroforesterie en Wallonie et à Bruxelles (AWAF)</i> – Association for the Promotion of Agroforestry in Wallonia and Brussels
CH	<i>Eidgenössisches Departement für Wirtschaft, Bildung und Forschung (WFB)</i> – Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research
CZ	<i>Česka Zemědělská Univerzita v Praze (CZU)</i> – Czech University of Life Sciences Prague
CZ	<i>Výzkumný Ústav Silva Taroucy Pro Krajinu a Okrasné Zahradnictví (VUKOZ)</i> – The Silva Tarouca Research Institute for Landscape
DE	<i>Deutscher Fachverband für Agroforstwirtschaft e.V. (DeFAF)</i> – German Agroforestry Association
DK	Regen Farmer
ES	<i>Universidad de Extremadura (UEx)</i> – University of Extremadura
FI	European Forest Institute (EFI)
FR	<i>Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement (INRAE)</i> – National Research Institute for Agriculture, Nutrition and the Environment
GR**	<i>Ελληνικό Αγροδασικό Δίκτυο (HAN)</i> – Greek Agroforestry Network
HU**	<i>Magyar Permakultúra Egyesület (MAPER)</i> – Hungarian Permaculture Association
IT	Università di Pisa (uniPI) – University of Pisa
LV**	Latvian Forest Owners' Association (LFOA)
NL	<i>Louis Bolk Instituut (LBI)</i>
PT	<i>Moinhos de Vento Agroecology Research Centre (MVARC)</i>
SL	<i>Sinergise Laboratorij za Geografske Informacijske Sisteme (SLGIS)</i>
UK	Farm Woodland Forum and Cranfield University

**EURAF affiliated partners.

To motivate country representatives, a presentation on the method to populate the agroforestry map of Europe with a question and answer session was held at the EURAF conference in Brno (Hübner and

Tylkowski, 2024a; 2024b). In the following months, the selected organisations in Table 5 were contacted by DeFAF via e-mail (Appendix A). The plan is that the organisations will gather the required information in the appropriate national language. A feedback system took place, where additional categories received colour coding to highlight additions requiring additional translation or verification. This included the overall English language version.

4. Phase four: Collection strategies – Examples from selected countries

Field day data gathering: workshop and excursion in Saxony, Germany

On the 8th of November 2024, over 35 interested people came together in the Region of *Lommatzcher Pflege*, Saxony (Figure 6). Some participants already had ideas for their land, while others were interested in the lease regulations that apply when timber is planted on arable land. Others came purely out of interest in agroforestry or agricultural transitions, or to expand their network of contacts in the region. Typical questions were: Which system best suits my needs? How expensive is it? Who will you support me with the implementation and how can I get funding? Who could I cooperate with?

Figure 6. Impressions from an “offline” mapping workshop in Saxony, in the southern periphery to the German DigitAF living lab.

An interactive activity with a printed map was organised where each participant was able to introduce themselves and place their site on the map of Saxony, using colour coded stickers resembling the categories of the new agroforestry map of Europe. The discussion also touched upon the potential benefits of mapping agroforestry stakeholders in the region. This campaign took place as part of the first meeting of the DeFAF Saxony regional group, which was newly founded this year.

Online data gathering and telephone survey

Some of the information, especially for the up- and downstream value chains related to agroforestry are available on the internet. For example, the database of tree nurseries is available online for some countries (e.g. for Germany: Bund deutscher Baumschulen (BdB) e.V. 2025). However, in agroforestry, the demand for, for example fruit trees, is based on the supply of high-stem fruit cultivars. Unfortunately, this information could only be reliably determined by phoning each organisation. In the Brandenburg area, which serves as the German Living Lab for DigitAF, a total of 22 tree nurseries could confirm selling of high stem trees. Furthermore, 41 fruit pressing companies or initiatives could be identified within the Brandenburg living lab area, of which seven operate mobile facilities. Under the heading of “Education and research”, there can be an interest in pomological show gardens or educational trails. From the regional government, a list of 11 of such facilities were found (Landtag Brandenburg, 2021). Additionally, 16 community or solitary farming initiatives (SoLaWi) were identified, from which several qualify as the fourth agroforestry system termed “Other” (Figure 7). During 2025, DeFAF is seeking to contact these stakeholders to determine if they are interested to add themselves to the Agroforestry Map of Europe.

Figure 7. Map of the DigitAF living lab in the Brandenburg region of Germany and surroundings showing the location of tree nurseries with a range of standard trees (green), fruit processing facilities (red), CSA - community supported agriculture (brown), and pomological show gardens and educational trails (blue).

Data processing from existing databases – UK and Ireland example

Although there was a map of agroforestry in the UK and Ireland (Figure 8), there have been queries about whether the data is fully GDPR compliant. Hence discussions were held between staff from Cranfield University (DigitAF partner), the Organic Research Centre (ORC) and the University of Reading (REFOREST project partners), and office holders from the Farm Woodland Forum to determine the best way forward. Two steps were taken to ensure full GDPR compliance. First, ethical approval for a new survey was obtained through Cranfield University’s ethics system. Second, in October 2024, a voluntary form was circulated via the Farm Woodland Forum (the organisation representing the UK in EURAF) to ensure that participant consent was obtained for all data to be added into the Agroforestry Map of Europe. After approval from the national administrator, data will be transferred into the back-end spreadsheet of the map and new entries will be created.

Figure 8. Previous map of agroforestry in the United Kingdom and Ireland (Farm Woodland Forum 2024).

Following the initial contact, about 38 agroforestry sites or businesses were identified across the UK and Ireland. The manager of the Farm Woodland Forum map, currently from the ORC, contacted selected members directly to inform them of the Agroforestry Map of Europe and obtain direct consent to participate in the initiative.

Data collection in the Netherlands based on the Agroforestry Netwerk Nederland map

The Dutch *Agroforestry Netwerk Nederland* (2024) map was developed for the Netherlands mainly by RVO (Netherlands Enterprise Agency). It covers seven types of agroforestry systems: 1) alley cropping (woody plants and arable crops), 2) riparian buffers, 3) fodder trees, 4) fruit-bearing trees on grassland, 5) fruit trees on grassland, 6) food forests, and 7) other, however a multiple choice is possible. The map also makes it possible to filter by soil type (marine clay, river clay, loam, sand, and loess) and different elements present in agroforestry systems (nut production, fruit trees, fruit shrubs, fodder trees, trees for quality wood, trees for biomass production, dairy cattle, beef cattle, poultry, pigs, and other). By the end of 2024, only agroforestry farms are included, with the ambition to add other stakeholders in the future. In total, 28 agroforestry sites can be found on the map (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Agroforestry map of the Netherlands (Agroforestry Netwerk Nederland 2024).

Further data collection is taking place in different stages. In the first stage, Dutch entries from the AGFORWARD and EURAF map are being contacted by Louis Bolk Institute (LBI), explaining the agroforestry map and its benefits for farmers. If farmers are willing to participate, the necessary data is then collected in an Excel format based on the template created by DeFAF. As of November 2024, data collection was currently in this stage but will be changed to the automated online format in the future.

In the second stage, existing entries on the *Agroforestry Netwerk Nederland* map will be contacted with the same explanation and asked if they are willing to participate. Again, the necessary data will be collected in a spreadsheet format based on the same fields as the new agroforestry map of Europe. In the third stage, regional agroforestry networks in the Netherlands will be contacted to find out which agroforestry areas, organizations and initiatives they would like to include on the map. These

areas, organizations and initiatives will be called with the same explanation and asked if they are willing to participate. Again, the necessary data will be collected in an Excel format based on the first template created by DeFAF.

In the Netherlands, direct personal contact with stakeholders is highly valued. It is important because communication lines are short in the Netherlands and they want to ensure the country is well represented on the map. Experience shows that direct personal contact reduces the risk of stakeholders not adding their data and ensures a good representation of the country's achievements.

The Netherlands is planning to continue approaching stakeholders directly. They will also ask regional network leaders to alert stakeholders in their region of the map and encourage them to participate. The map will be available on the *Agroforestry Netwerk Nederland* website (<https://www.agroforestrynetwork.nl/>). Currently, there is no data available focusing on products and services in the existing map. Still, they are exploring the possibility of hiring an intern to conduct a thorough analysis of Dutch agroforestry products and services. For now, they have focused on research departments and responsible individuals.

Italy – Data collection from previous projects and collaboration with an NGO

The agroforestry mapping for Italy at the national level was carried out through a methodical process that involved various data sources and collaboration between research institutions, universities, and local stakeholders. The first step was the retrieval and updating of existing data from previous regional projects. These data, collected in different areas of the country, were reviewed and integrated with the most recent information to ensure an up-to-date view of the distribution and characteristics of agroforestry in Italy. In parallel, data were derived from the existing EURAF map, and university and research organisations such as the University of Pisa. This information enriched the map and provided precise local references on agroforestry practices. In addition, data were also derived from the Italian DigitAF living lab. The living lab participants, composed of farmers, sector professionals, and other local stakeholders, contributed with direct information and practical observations.

A key step was also establishing contact with DEAFAL, an NGO that conducted a preliminary agroforestry mapping at the national level. Currently, agreements are in progress for the joint management of the collected data, which will allow the integration of existing information with new updates.

For future developments, the involvement of the national association and other NGOs interested in agroforestry is planned, to increase the volume of data on the new Agroforestry Map of Europe to foster collaboration among different sector actors.

Data collection in Belgium – example from the Region of Flanders

An initial map of agroforestry in the Flanders region was created by WERVEL contacting Flemish agroforestry farmers. If farmers were willing to participate, data was collected following the format created by DeFAF. More recently, the data collection has been progressed by ILVO, who took over the map from WERVEL. During this change, the data entry format was adjusted to the new format for the European map of agroforestry. During this process, it was decided to collect data separately for Flanders and Wallonia because Belgium has two agroforestry consortia and thus two EURAF representatives. Once data is collected for both regions, it will be possible to merge data from Flanders and Wallonia to have an overview of Belgium. As only agroforestry farmers were called in the first stage, it was important to bring awareness of the map to a broader public.

By bringing awareness about the agroforestry map to the broader public during this event, a promising development was visible in the number of responses on the online surveys. In order to do so, the following tasks were carried out:

1. Online surveys were created to collect more data on farmers and value-chain organisations, following a similar structure as mentioned in Appendix C (in Dutch) for Farmers (<https://forms.office.com/e/VFP1JWCnrG>) and the value chain (<https://forms.office.com/e/Fv0aQOZWri>)
2. For farmers who did not respond to the phone call in the first stage, an email was sent including a link to the survey.
3. To make the agroforestry map even more visible for website visitors of Agroforestry Flanders, a page was created explaining the agroforestry map including links to the online surveys (Agroforestry Vlaanderen 2024).
4. In one of the newsletters of Agroforestry Flanders, the map was promoted by a short text and a link to the website with more detailed information.
5. In the new handbook *Agroforestry in Flanders: 2014-2024* (currently in Dutch), chapter 2.4 “*Vlaamse agroforestry kaart*” features the agroforestry map (Reubens, Van Colen et al. 2024).
6. During the event “Farmers with trees: on the way to 2035” (original in Dutch “*Boeren met bomen: op weg naar 2035*”) on 15 October 2024, the agroforestry map was pitched in front of an audience of 200 people (including researchers, policymakers, teachers, farmers, landscape architects, value-chain organisations, etc.). In five minutes, the benefits of the map were portrayed and a demonstration of the new prototype map was given to show the map’s potential (ILVO 2024).
7. In a workshop by Carton (2024) two online videos in English (produced by DeFAF) were presented. The audience’s enthusiasm showed a big interest in the new agroforestry map.

The overall activities in the data collection process resulted in adding 104 agroforestry areas, seven organisations, and seven value-chain organisations to the Agroforestry Map of Flanders. New entries for the Region of Flanders can be added through the website of Agroforestry in Flanders: <https://www.agroforestryvlaanderen.be/en/agroforestrykaart> by clicking on the “Green Plus” symbol.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 A new Agroforestry Map of Europe

The Agroforestry Map of Europe can be viewed and accessed at the continent level in English and has been published on the DigitAF website (<https://digitaf.eu/agroforestry-map>) (DigitAF, 2024). It has also been published on the website of the sister project REFOREST (<https://agroforest.eu/tools/>) (REFOREST, 2024) via i-frame (Figure 10). By clicking on the top left-hand filtering symbol, it is possible to access information more specific on four areas of agroforestry interest (Figure 10). The map on the EU level <https://euraf.map.agroforestry-map.eu/> is integrated on the main website of the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF) (<https://www.euraf.net>). Linking and publishing of the map on unauthorised website is technically excluded.

Figure 10. Screenshots of the Agroforestry Map of Europe (DigitAF 2025, REFOREST 2025).

3.2 New national maps of agroforestry

Because of the Agroforestry Map of Europe was developed by collating national preferences of existing maps, the new mapping framework will remain on the creation of national agroforestry maps (Figure 11). New entries to the Agroforestry Map of Europe will therefore be possible through the respective national maps. It is anticipated that the national agroforestry organisations affiliated to EURAF will publish these national maps on their respective websites. It is also aimed to include links to the national maps and contacts in the country specific webpages of the EURAF website.

Figure 11. The framework for the European Map of Agroforestry allows individual nations, such as in this example the UK and Belgium, to manage their own national maps.

These national maps have been designed to display the data in the national languages and English. To facilitate the overview while zooming in and out, multiple entries of the same category are shown together using “spring embedder” technology.

As of October 2025, data have been collated for the United Kingdom, the Flanders region of Belgium, the Netherlands, Italy, Czechia and Germany (Appendix B and C). During the remainder of the DigitAF and REFOREST projects, the data collection process will continue and be rolled out to other countries with the support of EURAF.

3.3 Current and future use for data visualisation and evaluation

A development of the new map compared to previous versions is the additional focus on the whole value chain of the agroforestry sector and organisations or agencies working in the field. This includes the addition of organisations in the upstream and downstream sectors such as advisory services, tree nurseries, and purchasers of agroforestry products. Someone accessing the website can filter the entries according to their interest. A spatial search has the potential, for example, to allow the user to locate tree nurseries regionally.

The map and the associated database also allows national organisations to generate annual reports of the performance of agroforestry activities. For example, DeFAF in Germany has mapped the additional areas of agroforestry systems registered on the map from 1993 to 2024 (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Annual establishment (hectares per year) of registered systems on the Germany agroforestry map from 1993 to 2024.

National organisations can evaluate the map data to calculate the total area of registered agroforestry sites using the data export function to Microsoft Excel. For example, in December 2024, the Germany database recorded 1,687 ha of agroforestry across 201 sites, a 60 % increase from 2023 to 2024 (DeFAF e.V. 2024). The data can also be presented by region (example in Figure 13).

Figure 13. Distribution of agroforestry system types by regions in Germany as of December 2024. The DigitAF living lab region of Brandenburg is highlighted in blue.

3.4 Current and future use to foster networking within and beyond the living labs

The use of the Agroforestry Map of Europe allows the users to identify and contact agroforestry actors on the European level or in their respective country or region. This may be more convenient on the level of the national maps, as data is provided in their respective languages. The filtering mechanisms allows for specific searches, for example for tree species or products. Therefore networking can be a direct benefit of the map.

The established framework also allows national groups to explicitly mark “Lighthouse Farms” or “Agroforestry Ambassadors”. These are intended to highlight farms or farmers that have been active in the dissemination of agroforestry, e.g. offering agri-tourism with tours or events related to agroforestry or participate in research projects.

3.5 Next steps, data collection and maintenance

The Agroforestry Map of Europe is displayed on the EURAF website (<https://www.euraf.net>), and the plan is for the map to have its own bespoke web-page before the end of 2025: during October 2025, there were advanced discussions to increase the profile of the map on the EURAF website. For a common visualisation, the default language would need to be in English.

A second planned development is to allow users to add photographs of the agroforestry sites. The software used by the map will rescale photographs to a standard format to facilitate the user experience and it will include some identification demonstrating that it is linked to the map. Anyone wanting to use the photos will be instructed to contact the copyright holder and ask for permission.

During the remainder of the DigitAF and REFOREST projects, efforts will focus on enhancing the map by encouraging data-gathering from existing and additional countries. The plan is the continued collection and maintenance of the data will be largely completed by national organisations who will display national maps on their respective websites. We are also in discussion with the EU Agro4Adapt project (AgroForAdapt, 2025), who have a map of agroforestry products in Spain and Southern Spain to explore how that data could be made available to the new Agroforestry Map of Europe.

Now that working versions of the map are available on the DigitAF and REFOREST websites, a focus for the next 8 months will be to promote the Agroforestry Map of Europe at national and European levels to increase its usage. This has been discussed with the national organisations and will continue throughout the remaining project duration and beyond with support of EURAF. National strategies and campaigns could be developed in country specific dissemination plans e.g. through national agroforestry associations. For example, in the UK, Belgium and Germany the website has been promoted through postcards and leaflets at public events, and through articles in newsletters and social media.

For data updating, users of the map from selected countries, are already able to make or edit their entry directly on the national maps. In those countries, national agroforestry organisations are already encouraging the agroforestry community to details about agroforestry sites, services, and products. The DigitAF project team are in discussion with EURAF on how to promote this process to other countries.

4 Acknowledgements

The DigitAF project (Grant Agreement N° 101059794) is co-funded by the European Commission, European Research Agency, within the Horizon Europe programme, Cluster 6: "Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment". The views and opinions expressed in this report are purely those of the writers and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.

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Appendix A. Information sent to national representatives

Dear Friends of the NEW Agroforestry Map of Europe,

Thank you for your valuable input in populating the map. Since the AGFORWARD map, many more activities in agroforestry have developed. Therefore, each country's representative has the chance to add that information to the map. To do so, we set up this individual file for you where you can include information as bulk, or transfer collections, datasets that you may have collected over the years more comfortably. At a later stage, each entry will have to be done one by one.

I would kindly ask everyone to respect EU GDPR rules and not to make the file publicly available, e.g. via changing the access rights to "everyone with the link can access". If you have questions on how to proceed, I am here to help out. Please also consult Hübner and Tylkowski (2024) from the EURAF conference in Brno on the map, which contains a link to the prototype.

Some important notes on how to fill in data:

- All information added should be in the native language of the resp. country,
- Cells that need information to be added (e.g. contact) should be completed in your local language, no translation to EN is necessary as this will be done centralized.
- I would kindly ask you not to change the order of the categories in columns A, and B.
- In case you are unhappy with the translation from English to your local language, please feel free to make further amendments but add a note in Google Cell so we can track your change.
- Each agroforestry plot (a), each interested farm (i), organization (o), up-and downstream (ud) will receive a unique column and identifier (e.g. UK_a_001 for an agroforestry farm/plot entry from the UK and its running number)
- The IDs for the plots are to be repeated in the columns for tree species and shrub species.
- Cells that need confirmation only, just add a "1" (e.g. tree species list)
- In case you miss some categories /pieces of information, please try to incorporate under the category "other" that is available at various times (e.g. missing tree species) or incorporate it into the 2000-character description text.
- Old EURAF map entries will also be included, I would kindly ask you to review these and add additional information where applicable.
- In case you would like photos of each plot, etc., please collect them in a folder and rename them starting with the ID. We will create an upload function where all photos will be rescaled and marked with a water print to clearly show their belonging to the AF-map of Europe.
- Colour coding:
 - Categories in green highlighting are mandatory.
 - In the tree and shrub list, species taken from the European Tree Worker list are indicated in Dark Green.
 - Species indicated in purple have been added by a partner.

Appendix B. Example for a covering letter and online survey form to collect data in the UK

UK Agroforestry Map for EURAF

Page 1 – Introduction

Two European Horizon projects, DigitAF and REFOREST, are working together to update the European map of agroforestry, which will be hosted by the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF). As part of this initiative, UK partners from each project are working with the Farm Woodland Forum to develop a single, unified database of agroforestry in the UK.

By completing this form you will be able to have your agroforestry site recognised at a national and European scale. The data submitted will be held by the UK Farm Woodland Forum and integrated into the national map of agroforestry on the Farm Woodland Forum website. The same data will also be shared with EURAF for uploading on to a European map on the EURAF website.

Consent statements for data protection will be provided at the end of the form. No data will be submitted until these statements are selected.

This form should take no longer than 10 minutes to complete.

Acknowledgement

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101060635 (REFOREST) and No. 101059794 (DigitAF). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

An * after the question indicates that it is required.

Page 2 – Basic Information and Contact Details

Name and location are required, but contact details are optional.

1. Site name *
2. Location (co-ordinates or address) *
3. Contact Person Name
4. Email
5. Website
6. Which category do you fit into? *
 - a. Existing agroforestry site – *if selected then user proceeds to page 3*
 - b. Interested/potential agroforestry site – *if selected then user proceeds to page 7*
 - c. Agroforestry related organisation i.e. research, policy, NGO. – *if selected then user proceeds to page 9*
 - d. Supply chain organisation i.e. tree nursery, product processor, consulting firm. – *if selected then user proceeds to page 10*

Page 3 – Agroforestry Site Description - Existing

7. Please provide a short description of your agroforestry site (2000 characters max)*
8. What would you describe your farm/site as? (multiple can be selected) *
 - a. Arable farming
 - b. Fodder production
 - c. Livestock farming
 - d. Energy production
 - e. Fruit growing
 - f. Wood production
 - g. Direct sale available
 - h. Agritourism offered
 - i. Other – *use can enter their own answer*
9. Which of these best fits your agroforestry system type? *
 - a. Silvoarable system (woody perennials and arable crops including intercropped permanent crops e.g. grapevine)
 - b. Silvopastoral system (woody perennials and livestock including grazed permanent crops)
 - c. Agrosilvopastoral system (woody perennials, arable crops and livestock together)
 - d. Other – *user can enter their own answer*
10. What is the size of your agroforestry system? (ha) *
11. Roughly, what percentage of this area is under shrub/tree canopy? (%) *
12. What date were the shrubs/trees planted? (if multiple dates then give the earliest) *

Page 4 – Shrubs/trees and products

13. Which tree species have been planted as part of this agroforestry system (common or scientific names)
14. What is the intended use of the trees? (multiple can be selected)
 - a. Production biofuel
 - b. Production stemwood (timber)
 - c. Food production (e.g. production fruit/nut)
 - d. Environmental benefits (including carbon, windbreaks, animal welfare, biodiversity)
 - e. Cultural benefits (including recreation, landscape, etc.)
 - f. Other – *user can enter their own answer*
15. Which shrub species have been planted as part of this agroforestry system (common or scientific names)
16. What is the intended use of the shrubs? (multiple can be selected)

- a. Production biofuel
- b. Production stemwood (timber)
- c. Food production (e.g. production fruit/nut)
- d. Environmental benefits (including carbon, windbreaks, animal welfare, biodiversity)
- e. Cultural benefits (including recreation, landscape, etc.)
- f. Other – *user can enter their own answer*

Page 5 – Livestock and Crops

17. Which livestock species, if any, are or have been present in the agroforestry system? (multiple can be selected)
- a. Poultry
 - b. Cattle
 - c. Sheep (including goats)
 - d. Pigs
 - e. None
 - f. Other – *user can enter their own answer*
18. Which crops, if any, are or have been present in the agroforestry system? (multiple can be selected)
- a. Pasture (e.g. grass, clover and herbal leys)
 - b. Wheat
 - c. Barley
 - d. Oats
 - e. Field beans
 - f. Peas
 - g. Oilseed rape
 - h. Lupin
 - i. Lucerne (alfalfa)
 - j. Vegetables (i.e. horticulture)
 - k. Potatoes
 - l. Medicinal or aromatic herbs
 - m. Maize
 - n. Flax
 - o. Rye
 - p. Sunflower
 - q. Sugar beet
 - r. Durum wheat
 - s. Mustard
 - t. Spelt
 - u. Grapevine
 - v. Flowers and ornamental plants
 - w. Other – *user can enter their own answer*

Page 6 – Motivations and Interests – Existing

19. Are there major constraints on your agroforestry site? (multiple can be selected) *
- a. Drought / low water holding capacity
 - b. Low soil fertility
 - c. Susceptibility to erosion
 - d. Species poor site
 - e. Landscape with few structures / landscape elements
 - f. Other – *user can enter their own answer*
20. Are you interested in the sale of products from your agroforestry system? *

- a. Yes
 - b. No
21. What are your motivations for establishing the agroforestry system? (multiple can be selected) *
- a. Diversify product range
 - b. Increase crop or livestock productivity
 - c. Improve animal welfare
 - d. Enhance biodiversity
 - e. Improve soil health and/or control soil erosion
 - f. Reduce pollution into surface waters
 - g. Improve climate resilience or sequester carbon
 - h. Enhance landscape appearance
 - i. Other – *user can enter their own answer*

After this question users are sent to page 11.

Page 7 – Agroforestry Site Description – Potential

22. Please provide a short description of your potential agroforestry site (2000 characters max) *
23. Which of these best fits the type of agroforestry system you may implement? *
- a. Silvoarable system (woody perennials and arable crops including intercropped permanent crops e.g. grapevine)
 - b. Silvopastoral system (woody perennials and livestock including grazed permanent crops)
 - c. Agrosilvopastoral system (woody perennials, arable crops and livestock together)
 - d. Other – *user can enter their own answer*

Page 8 – Motivations and Interests – Potential

24. What are your motivations for establishing the agroforestry system? (multiple can be selected) *
- a. Diversify product range
 - b. Increase crop or livestock productivity
 - c. Improve animal welfare
 - d. Enhance biodiversity
 - e. Improve soil health and/or control soil erosion
 - f. Reduce pollution into surface waters
 - g. Improve climate resilience or sequester carbon
 - h. Enhance landscape appearance
 - i. Other – *user can enter their own answer*
25. What are the barriers to you implementing agroforestry onto your site? (multiple can be selected)
- a. Legal framework
 - b. Lack of or insufficient support
 - c. Ownership structure
 - d. Lack of experience and information
 - e. Uncertain economic returns
 - f. Other – *user can enter their own answer*

After this question users are sent to page 11.

Page 9 – Further Information – Organisations

26. Please provide a short description of your organisation (2000 characters max) *
27. What type of organisation do you represent? *
- a. Administration/public authority

- b. Business (including farms)
- c. University / College
- d. Research institution / other institution
- e. Association/federation/NGO
- f. Other – *user can enter their own answer*

Page 10 – Further Information – Supply Chain

28. Please provide a short description of your organisation (2000 characters max) *
29. What type of organisation do you represent?
- a. Consultant or consulting firm
 - b. Tree nursery
 - c. Contractor
 - d. Nut/fruit processor
 - e. Wood processor
 - f. Purchase and/or sale of agroforestry products
 - g. Sale of agricultural inputs and materials
 - h. Other – *user can enter their own answer*
30. What are your main products/services?
31. Are you interested in labelling and branding around agroforestry?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
32. Do you currently refer to agroforestry on your labelling or branding?
- a. Yes
 - b. No

After this question users are sent to page 11.

Page 11 – Confirmation of data sharing

33. I confirm that this data can be used for the national map database of agroforestry in the UK, hosted by the Farm Woodland Forum. *
34. I am aware that the name, e-mail, location and information provided will be publicly available.
35. I am aware that I request modification or withdrawal of the information by contacting: *email*.
- a. Yes
36. I confirm that this data can be used for the European map database of agroforestry in the UK, hosted by the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF). *
- a. Yes

On submission users are given the message:

Thank you for your submission. To make changes or request deletion of your data, please contact *email*.

Appendix C. Data collection and promotion of the map in Flanders

Example Mail to stakeholder from Flanders

Dear [name],

The Consortium Agroforestry Flanders is involved in an initiative to create a **digital agroforestry map** for Europe, for which we are focusing on agroforestry in Belgium. The goal is to put on the map as many agroforestry farmers as possible, but also relevant organizations (e.g. nut harvester sellers, fruit processors and advisors) for agroforestry businesses. My colleague Jeroen Watté has called nearly 150 agroforestry farmers for this purpose and a large proportion are already included in this map. Unfortunately he had not been able to reach you by phone, but through this mail I hope to reach you still.

If you are also interested in having your farm included in the digital agroforestry map, we would like to ask you to fill out a short Microsoft Forms survey where you can confirm your consent and complete some details. The survey will take approximately 5-8 minutes to complete. Only upon giving your consent through the survey will we be able to include your company on the map.

The link to the survey can be found here: <https://forms.office.com/e/VFP1JWCnrG>

If you have any questions or comments, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Thank you in advance for your time, we would greatly appreciate your input.

Website item

This website item is translated into English from [Zet jouw organisatie op de Agroforestry Kaart - Agroforestry](#):

The new, interactive European Agroforestry Map is about to be launched, thanks to an intense collaboration between EURAF and several projects including Reforest, DigitAF and - specifically for the Flemish component - Agroforestry 2025. This easy-to-read map, which shows not only agroforestry plots but also the up- and downstream sector, advisors, research institutions and other agroforestry actors, offers many opportunities and benefits:

- **Encourage cooperation:** cooperation among farmers can be interesting for economies of scale. Think of joint execution of planting or maintenance works, joint purchase of machinery or planting materials. In addition, farmers can find other links in the chain, such as consultants, contractors and buyers of products.
- **Organize sales market and supply chain:** buyers can see where certain products can be found. At the same time, farmers can see where nurserymen or other suppliers are located.
- **Education, knowledge exchange and research:** ideal for organizing an information session or site visit in collaboration with a field company, and also makes it easier for students or researchers to contact agroforestry applicators.
- **Policy:** the evolution, characteristics and distribution of agroforestry in Flanders (and by extension Europe) is relevant for policy actors and can help to concretize certain ambitions and actions (locally) and the impact of certain measures.

The map is provided with useful symbols that facilitate your search. Symbols are linked to (1) a type of agroforestry system or (2) to a theme, namely:

Type of agroforestry system

- Silvicultural system (trees and shrubs combined with plant production)
- Silvopastoral system (trees and shrubs combined with animal production)
- Agrosilvopastoral system (trees and shrubs combined with plant and animal production)
- Other systems (incl. "home gardens," food forests, etc.)

Themes

- Up-&Downstream sector, private services, service providers, nurseries, and so on;
- Scientific institutions, education, public agencies, and so on;
- Agroforestry companies;
- Interested parties (those currently thinking about establishing an agroforestry plot).

Users control what personal information (address, company details, photo, etc.) is displayed on the map. For all data, we as administrator ensure that changes are screened by the user before it appears online. In the process, each newly uploaded photo is automatically resized and watermarked to mark the source of the map. The resulting map data is protected and its management is structured and transparent. We take all measures necessary to comply with data protection legislation.

Would you like your agroforestry business, organization, or service to participate in this initiative? Let us know!

Interested in putting your **agroforestry business** on the agroforestry map? Then fill out the survey below:

Interested in putting your **value-chain organisation** on the agroforestry map? Then fill out the survey below:

As soon as the agroforestry map is online, we will share the link. From then on, it will be even easier to put your data on the map.